

An Empirical Analysis of Weak Form Efficiency in Bombay Stock Exchange Sectoral Indices

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 2

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.112

Citation:

Rajesh Ramkumar, R., and K. Dhanalakshmi. "An Empirical Analysis of Weak Form Efficiency in Bombay Stock Exchange Sectoral Indices." *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, vol. 6, no. S2, 2019, pp. 59–64.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591088>

R.Rajesh Ramkumar

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College, Sivakasi, Virudhunagar District
Tamil Nadu, India*

Dr.K.Dhanalakshmi

*Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration
Ayya Nadar Janaki Ammal College, Sivakasi, Virudhunagar District
Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

Capital Market deals with medium and long term funds. It is an institutional arrangement for borrowing medium and long term funds. The sectoral analysis is typically employed by investors who plan to select better stocks to invest. Hence the study of Sectoral Efficiency could provide useful input to the Government, Policymakers and Investors to identify the efficient sectors. This study tested the Market Efficiency of BSE (Nine) Sectoral Indices by using daily share price returns during the study period. The study found that did not follow random distribution during the study period. The study advices investors to invest their money in BSE Bankex as it performed well during the study period.

Keywords: Weak Form Efficiency, Sectoral Indices, Autocorrelation Function

Introduction

A stock market index is one which indicates the pattern of movements of the prices of a group of securities which are considered to be the representative sample of the entire stock market. The stock market index is an invaluable guide to study the trend of growth patterns in the economy to analyse as well as forecast business cycles and also to correlate stock market indices to various economic activities.

The term, Market Efficiency, in capital market theory is used to explain the degree to which the stock prices reflect all available and relevant information. The concept of Efficiency Market Hypothesis (EMH) explains how the anticipated price of an asset fluctuates randomly (Samuelson - 1965). It presented a formal theory and evidence for market efficiency and subsequently revised it further on the basis of development in research (Fama - 1991).

Review of Literature

An attempt has been made in this section to review the earlier research works undertaken in the area of capital market efficiency to understand the research gap and methodology adopted by researchers in the earlier studies.

Bhanu Panit and Bishnoi T.R (2001) analysed the behavior of daily and weekly returns of five Indian Stock Market indices for random walk during the study period. The results revealed that Indian Stock Market indices did not follow random walk. Robert T. Kleiman, et.al (2002), studied the weak form efficiency for international commercial real estate markets, utilizing stock market indices of real estate for three geographical regions like Europe, Asia and North America. Hareesh Kumar. V and Malabeika Deo (2007) tested the information efficiency of Indian Securities Market with respect to a widely reported market anomaly. They found out the prevalence of Day-of-the-Week Effect in the Indian Stock Market, which was attached both to the stock return and volatility and thus proved the Indian Stock Market to be efficient. Francesco Guidi, et.al (2010) explored the weak form of the efficient market hypothesis for Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) equity markets.

Statement of the Problem

Capital Market is a vital institution that facilitates economic development of the country. It is true that so many parties are interested in understanding the efficiency of the Capital Market. Besides, majority of investors do not have an idea about which index is the best in India for investment. In India, very few studies have examined the daily returns, weekly returns and monthly returns of stock indices. Besides, there has been no comprehensive study carried out to test the efficiency of sectoral indices of a stock exchange in the Indian context. Hence the present study to investigate the efficiency of Sectoral Indices of Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) by using the daily returns.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are to examine the efficiency in BSE Sectoral Indices.

Hypotheses of the Study

In the light of the objectives, the following Null Hypotheses were developed and tested.

NH1: There is no normal distribution in the returns of BSE Sectoral Indices

NH2: There is no weak form efficiency in the returns of BSE Sectoral Indices

Methodology of the Study

Sample Selection

The sample indices were selected by taking into account the following criteria.

1. Turnover of 50 crores and above (per day)
2. Availability of required data during the study period

There were totally 13 sectoral indices in BSE as on 21st June 2018. In the first stage, nine indices (70%), out of 13 indices, were selected as the sample size, based on its turnover values in the market. The required data for BSE FMCG, BSE Oil and Gas and BSE Realty Indices were not available. Therefore, only nine indices became eligible for selection. The details of sample indices listed in those sample six indices are given in Table-1.

Sources of Data

Data collected from BSE official website www.bseindia.com.

Period of the Study

The study period from 01st January 2012 to 31st December 2017.

Tools Used for Analysis

1. Descriptive Statistics
2. Autocorrelation

Limitations of the Study

The proposed study suffers from the following limitations.

1. The study was restricted to only BSE in India.
2. The study period covered only seven years from 2012 to 2017.
3. All the limitations associated with various tools like Descriptive Statistics, and Autocorrelation Function (ACF) Test are applicable to this study also.

Analysis of Random Walk and Market Efficiency in Sectoral Indices

1. Analysis of Normality of Returns Data for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices
2. Analysis of Market Efficiency for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices

Analysis of Normality of Returns Data for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices

Table-2 depicts the Descriptive Statistics for daily share price returns of the nine sample BSE Indices taken for this study. It is to be noted that the mean average returns were positive for all sample indices. However, the mean return was high for BSE Bankex, compared to the other sample indices considered for this study. It is significant to note that BSE Bankex earned high return (0.0841) while BSE Power Index accounted for the lowest return (0.0353) during the study period. The standard deviation of returns (risk) ranged from 1.25741 (BSE Health Care Index) to 2.51288 (BSE Metal Index). The BSE Metal Index earned the highest standard deviation (2.51288), which indicates the highest risk, followed by BSE Bankex (2.23450), BSE Consumer Durables Index (1.99640), BSE Power Index (1.97526), BSE IT Index (1.92238), BSE TECK Index (1.75342), BSE PSU Index (1.70934), BSE Automobile Index (1.67512) and BSE Health Care Index (1.25741). It is clearly understood from the analysis of skewness that out of 9 sample indices, 5 indices registered positive values, i.e BSE Bankex (0.317), BSE Information Technology Index (0.138), BSE Power Index (0.247), BSE PSU Index (0.146) and BSE TECK Index (0.175). The remaining four indices (BSE Automobile Index, BSE Consumer Durables Index, BSE Health Care Index, BSE Metal Index) earned negatively skewed values (-0.211, -0.185, -0.518 and -0.145 respectively). According to the analysis of Kurtosis, it is seen that out of 9 sample indices, all indices earned a value over the level of 3, it's called leptokurtic. It is clearly understood from the analysis of kurtosis that all the nine indices used in this study were not normally distributed during the study period. Hence the Null Hypothesis (NH1) "There is no normal distribution in the returns of BSE Sample Sectoral Indices", was accepted.

Analysis of Market Efficiency for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices

The results of autocorrelation for daily returns of the BSE Sectoral Indices during the study period from 01.01.2012 to 31.12.2017 are reported in Table-3. The analysis of autocorrelation coefficients shows the fact that BSE Automobile Index were significant at 5% level of significant, with positive value (0.144) for 1st lag. The autocorrelation results of BSE Bankex shows that out of 28 lags, three lags (1st, 8th and 26th lag) were significant at 95% level of confidence. It is noted that the highest magnitude of coefficient was 0.135 at lag one during the study period. It is clearly understood that the autocorrelation coefficient value of BSE Health Care Index was significant at 5% level and there were positive values for 1st, 13th 14th, 17th and 28th lags during the study period. The analysis of BSE IT Index clearly shows the fact that out of 28 lags, only one lag (17th lag) was significant while the remaining lags were insignificant at 5% level of significance. The autocorrelation analysis was performed for 28 lags of daily returns for BSE Metal Index during the study period. It was found that the autocorrelation coefficients for 1st lag, 8th lag and 17th lag were significant at 5% level of significance for BSE Metal Index. The results of autocorrelation

coefficient for BSE Power Index during the study period indicate the fact that the autocorrelation coefficients were significant at 95% of confidence level, with positive values at 1st, 8th, 14th and 17th lags during the study period. The analysis of PSU Index indicates that the autocorrelation coefficients were significant at 95% of confidence level, with positive values at 1st, 7th, 8th, 14th and 26th lags during the study period. It is noted that the positive value sign of the autocorrelation coefficient clearly shows that the daily returns of PSU Index tended to be the same sign on consecutive days. From the analysis of BSE TECK Index, it is seen that out of 28 lags, only one lag (17th lag) was significant during the study period. The remaining lags were insignificant at the 95% of confidence level. Thus the Null Hypothesis (NH4) “There is no weak form efficient in the returns of BSE Sample Sectoral Indices”, was accepted.

Findings of the Study

The following are the important findings and suggestions of the study.

1. The analysis of Autocorrelation indicates that out of nine sample indices, two indices (BSE Health Care Index and BSE PSU Index) showed positive and significant autocorrelation value only at five lags out of 28 lags.
2. From the analysis, it is suggested that retail investors may invest their hard earned money in BSE Bankex as it performed well during the study period.

Conclusion

An attempt has been made in this study to investigate the weak form efficiency in the Indian Stock Market by examining the returns of nine sample indices. The Autocorrelation revealed that out of nine indices, 2 indices (BSE Health Care Index and BSE PSU Index) earned positive values and were significant at 5% level at more number of lags. As mentioned earlier, this research mainly looked for the evidence of weak form efficiency by hypothesizing the normality of the distribution series and random walk assumption. The Regulators and Policy Makers should pay attention to the performance of indices in the market.

References

1. Asha E Thomas, and Dileep Kumar, M.C. (2010), “Empirical Evidence on Weak Form Efficiency of Indian Stock Market”, *Asia Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 8, 59-68.
2. Bhanu Panit and Bishnoi, T.R. (2001), “Testing Random Walk Hypothesis for Indian Stock Market Indices”, (Electronic Copy available at <http://www.utiicm/cmc/pdf/2002/bhanupanit.pdf>)
3. Hareesh Kumar, V. and Malabika Deo (2007), “Efficiency of Indian Stock Market: A Case of Day of the Week Effect”, *SMART Journal of Business Management Studies*, 3(2), 28-35.
4. Khan, A.Q., Sana Ikram and Mariyam Mehtab (2011), “Testing Weak Form Market Efficiency of Indian Capital Market: A Case of National Stock Exchange (NSE) and Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE)”, *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 3(6), 115-127.

Table-1 Name of BSE Sectoral Sample Indices Listed

Sl.No.	Name of the Indices
1	BSE Automobile Index
2	BSE Bankex
3	BSE Consumer Durables Index

4	BSE Health Care Index
5	BSE Information Technology Index
6	BSE Metal Index
7	BSE Power Index
8	BSE PSU Index
9	BSE TECK Index

Source: www.bseindia.com

Table-2 The Results of Normality of Data (Descriptive Statistics) for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices during the Study Period from 01.01.2012 to 31.12.2017

Descriptive Statistics\ Name of the Company & Index	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
BSE Automobile Index	0.0712	1.67512	-0.211	3.707
BSE Bankex	0.0841	2.23450	0.317	5.310
BSE Consumer Durables Index	0.0690	1.99640	-0.185	4.747
BSE Health Care Index	0.0632	1.25741	-0.518	5.438
BSE Information Technology Index	0.0428	1.92238	0.138	3.244
BSE Metal Index	0.0620	2.51288	-0.145	3.434
BSE Power Index	0.0374	1.97526	0.247	7.841
BSE PSU Index	0.0321	1.70934	0.146	8.108
BSE TECK Index	0.0352	1.75342	0.175	4.470

Source: Collected from PROWESS Corporate Database & Computed using SPSS (Version 19)

Table-3 The Results of Market Efficiency (Autocorrelation Test) for BSE Sample Sectoral Indices during the Study Period from 01.01.2012 to 31.12.2017

Lags	BSE Auto mobile Index	BSE Bankex	BSE CD Index	BSE HC Index	BSE IT Index	BSE Metal Index	BSE Power Index	BSE PSU Index	BSE TECK Index
1	0.144*	0.135*	0.087*	0.068*	0.016	0.117*	0.096*	0.128*	0.016
2	0.038	-0.005	0.027	0.028	-0.078	0.022	-0.007	0.034	-0.066
3	-0.027	-0.011	0.062*	0.008	-0.057	0.006	0.005	-0.004	-0.030
4	-0.014	-0.036	-0.029	-0.002	-0.012	-0.035	-0.013	-0.006	-0.014
5	-0.029	-0.059	0.018	-0.003	0.019	-0.001	-0.007	-0.041	-0.002
6	-0.013	-0.073	0.002	-0.036	-0.001	-0.004	-0.050	-0.056	-0.025
7	0.043	0.002	0.038	0.045	0.000	0.036	0.031	0.060*	-0.001
8	0.021	0.062*	0.036	0.031	0.032	0.085*	0.084*	0.071*	0.043
9	0.009	0.023	-0.016	-0.007	0.013	0.043	0.029	0.026	0.019
10	0.030	0.009	-0.000	0.043	0.020	-0.019	0.011	-0.001	0.027
11	0.013	0.023	0.009	0.009	-0.002	-0.033	-0.045	-0.045	-0.012

12	0.043	0.005	0.035	0.032	-0.006	0.003	-0.022	-0.015	-0.002
13	0.047	0.002	0.042	0.071*	-0.023	0.026	0.027	0.017	0.004
14	0.016	0.035	0.063*	0.064*	0.008	0.041	0.065*	0.069*	0.032
15	0.016	0.012	-0.003	-0.001	-0.005	0.038	0.027	0.024	-0.015
16	0.015	0.031	0.009	0.009	0.008	0.023	0.039	0.034	0.009
17	0.045	0.037	0.051*	0.065*	0.080*	0.054*	0.069*	0.046	0.089*
18	0.018	-0.023	-0.002	-0.017	0.021	-0.006	-0.004	-0.058	0.021
19	0.014	-0.028	0.024	-0.001	0.036	0.024	-0.002	-0.031	0.021
20	-0.043	-0.038	-0.025	-0.002	-0.051	-0.034	-0.043	-0.070	-0.070
21	-0.005	0.009	-0.026	-0.003	-0.016	-0.003	0.026	-0.001	-0.031
22	-0.021	0.023	-0.002	-0.024	0.007	0.019	0.000	0.000	0.011
23	-0.026	-0.003	-0.043	-0.060	-0.039	-0.016	-0.000	-0.007	-0.044
24	0.011	-0.013	-0.002	0.016	-0.011	0.003	0.028	0.032	0.006
25	0.047	0.032	0.046	-0.004	0.042	0.014	0.009	0.015	0.040
26	0.036	0.060*	0.004	0.025	0.027	0.041	0.027	0.050*	0.011
27	0.016	-0.019	0.003	-0.040	0.011	-0.013	-0.024	-0.047	0.007
28	-0.015	0.018	0.008	0.053*	-0.008	-0.002	0.012	-0.000	0.001

Source: Collected from PROWESS Corporate Database and Computed using SPSS (Version 19)

Note: * positive value at 5% level of significance